

Crop management

Stand establishment practices affect performance of intermediate deepwater rice

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Rice is either direct seeded or transplanted in rainfed lowlands of intermediate water depth (0-50 cm). Tillers removed from the direct seeded crop (clonal tillers) may be used as seedlings for transplanting, provided the parent crop is not adversely affected.

We compared the performance of intermediate rice under direct seeded and transplanted conditions where nursery-grown seedlings and clonal tillers were used. The study was made at Cuttack in 1989 using a semidwarf, long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive rice cultivar, CR1016, on alluvial sandy clay loam soil of medium fertility. Seed was direct sown on 30 May at 400 (normal) and 600 seeds/m² at 20-cm row spacing. Germination occurred when the rains came after sowing, with a 45% emergence rate. Water began accumulating in the field at 10 d after emergence (DE) but remained static at <10 cm until 40 DE (see figure).

Seedlings were transplanted on 30 Jul and 10 Aug with 3-4 nursery seedlings or clonal tillers/hill at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Nursery seedlings were raised in beds where 60 g seeds/m² were sown on 30 May.

The direct seeded crop with the higher seeding rate was thinned by uprooting some of the plants, including clonal tillers (100-120/m²), which were transplanted. Water level rose gradually to a peak depth of 60-65 cm at 55 and 80 DE and then receded to 0 cm by crop maturity. A common basal dose of 40 kg N, 8.7 kg P, and 16.7 kg k/ha was applied uniformly. The treatments were arranged in a randomized block design with three replications in 16-m² plots.

Plant height of direct seeded rice was similar under various seeding rates. In the transplanted crop, height was greater for clonal tillers than for nursery seedlings (see table). Tiller number on

Daily rainfall (vertical lines) and water depth (dotted line) variation in the field during premonsoon, monsoon, and postmonsoon periods. Cuttack, India, 1989.

10 Sep and panicles at maturity was not affected in the direct seeded crop (due to the removal of clonal tillers from the plots sown at 600 seeds/m²) when compared with the undisturbed crop sown at 400 seeds/m². Under transplanted conditions, however, tillers and panicles/m² were significantly less than under direct seeding, particularly in the late planted crop. This was caused by mortality of seedlings at or immediately after planting and by less tillering because of excess water stagnation.

Panicle weight was highest in the crop planted on 20 Jul. Lower panicle weight

Effect of direct seeding and transplanting on growth and yield attributes of rice variety CR1016 under intermediate deep water conditions. Cuttack, India 1989.

Treatment	Seedling vigor ^a		Plant height (cm)		Tillers/m ² on 10 Sep (no.)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
	Height	Dry weight (g/seedling)	10 Sep	Maturity					
Direct seeding									
30 May									
400 seeds/m ²			87	94	262	151	1.99	2.9	5.3
600 seeds/m ² (a)			83	92	277	146	1.94	2.9	4.8
600 seeds/m ² (b)			82	92	268	152	2.01	3.0	5.0
Transplanting									
20 Jul									
Nursery seedlings	40	0.48	86	108	130	125	2.54	3.0	5.7
Clonal tillers uprooted from (a)	43	0.85	98	112	153	144	2.68	3.4	6.0
10 Aug									
Nursery seedlings	70	0.64	80	100	76	65	1.76	1.4	2.7
Clonal tillers uprooted from (b)	80	0.96	96	110	85	76	1.95	1.8	3.5
SE			3	4	12	8	0.12	0.1	0.3
LSD (0.05)			10	12	37	26	0.36	0.3	0.9

^a Mean of 25 seedlings.

in the direct seeded crop was because of relatively more panicles/m²; in the 10 Aug transplanted crop, it was because of less dry matter accumulation from the shorter growth duration.

The crop transplanted on 20 Jul produced the highest grain yield, significantly more than that of the other treatments. The clonally propagated crop performed better than the others because it was taller, had more dry weight, and could acclimatize more easily to flooded conditions. The direct seeded crop was at par with the 20 Jul transplanted crop of nursery seedlings. Yield did not decrease with the removal of clonal tillers. Late transplanting resulted in the lowest yield because of fewer and lighter panicles. Clonal propagation was superior to nursery-grown seedlings.

Clonal tillers of rice uprooted from a well-established direct seeded crop may be planted for higher productivity under excess water conditions. This practice is promising for use when early flash floods have partially damaged a crop and nursery seedlings are not available for late planting. ■

Occurrence of ufra disease in different rice ecosystems in Bangladesh, 1991-93.

District	Season ^a	Sites visited (no.)	Affected area (ha)	Infestation (%)	Yield loss (%)	Cropping pattern ^b
Tangail	T. aman	2	180	80-100	80-100	4
	Boro	2	141	20-100	10-100	4
Gazipur	T. aman	16	132	30-100	20-100	4, 5, 6
	DWR	1	3	40-100	50-100	2
Dhaka	Boro	13	333	10-100	10-100	2, 4, 5, 6
	T. aus	2	3	10-100	10-50	4, 9
	T. aman	4	50	40-100	30-100	4, 6
Narayanganj	Boro	2	40	10-100	20-60	5, 6
	T. aus	1	10	10-40	10-40	5
	DWR	2	3	10-20	20-60	2, 6
Norshingdi	T. aman	2	40	30-100	20-100	4
	Boro	4	60	20-100	10-100	2, 5, 6
	T. aus	1	20	10-50	10-40	5
Comilla	DWR	2	12	40-80	20-80	2, 6
	Boro	1	5	10-50	10-30	2
Chandpur	DWR	23	1096	10-100	20-100	1, 2, 3, 6
	Boro	8	86	10-60	10-50	2, 6
Noakhali	DWR	3	6	50-100	40-100	1, 6
	Boro	2	30	10-30	10-20	2, 6
Gopalganj	DWR	1	4	60-600	40-100	1, 2, 6
	DWR	4	27	50-100	40-100	1, 2, 3, 6
Madaripur	DWR	3	12	30-80	40-80	1, 2
	T. aman	17	296	10-100	20-100	4, 7, 8
Barisal	Boro	10	83	10-100	10-100	2, 4, 5, 6
	T. aman	2	25	40-100	50-100	7
Jhalkati	T. aman	2	20	40-100	60-100	7
Potuakhali	T. aman	2	20	60-100	50-100	7, 8
Borguna	T. aman	3	35	10-70	30-50	4, 7, 9
Bhola	T. aman	5	400	40-100	40-100	4, 8
Pirojpur ^c	T. aman	2	200	10-100	20-100	9
Bagerhat	DWR	5	400	50-100	50-100	1
Norail ^c		147	3772			

^aDWR = deepwater rice. T. aman = transplanted aman, T. aus = transplanted aus. ^bCropping pattern: 1 = nonrice crops, 2 = DWR-Boro, 3 = DWR-fallow, 4 = T. aman-Boro, 5 = T. aman-Boro-T. aus, 6 = Boro-fallow, 7 = T. aman-pulse/wheat, 8 = T. aman-fallow, 9 = T. aman-T. aus. ^cBased on newspaper report.

Integrated pest management—diseases

Widespread ufra disease incidence in different rice ecosystems in Bangladesh

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Ufra disease, caused by the rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*, is a devastating disease of deepwater rice (DWR) in Bangladesh. It has also been occurring in rainfed lowland rice areas during transplanted aman (Jul-Nov), transplanted aus (Apr-Jun), and irrigated boro (Nov-Apr) seasons.

During 1991-93, we surveyed 147 locations under deepwater, transplanted aman, transplanted aus, and boro rice covering 3,772 ha infected with the disease (see table). Thirty-four thanas local administrative units) in 18 districts

Ufra distribution (●) in some districts of Bangladesh, 1991-93.

District boundary = ———, Thana boundary = - - - - - , district headquarter = ▲, 1 = Tangail, 2 = Gazipur, 3 = Dhaka, 4 = Narayanganj, 5 = Norshingdi, 6 = Comilla, 7 = Chandpur, 8 = Noakhali, 9 = Gopalganj, 10 = Madaripur, 11 = Barisal, 12 = Jhalkati, 13 = Potuakhali, 14 = Borguna, 15 = Bhola, 16 = Pirojpur, 17 = Bagerhat, 18 = Norail.

of southwestern Bangladesh were affected (see figure). In addition, farmers reported its occurrence in many other remote areas that we could not visit, making the total affected area much greater. The infection level for the rice crops was 10-100% with the boro crop being least affected under boro or boro-fallow patterns compared with transplanted aman - boro or transplanted aman - boro - transplanted aus patterns. Yield loss was estimated to range from 20 to 100% in transplanted aman and DWR, from 10 to 100% in boro rice, and from 10 to 50% in transplanted aus rice

(see table). Many fields had 100% crop loss, with the proportion higher in DWR and transplanted aman than in the boro crop.

Both local and modern rice varieties were susceptible to ufra disease.

Based on our observations and interviews with farmers, we identified several reasons for the spread of ufra disease in transplanted aman, boro, and transplanted aus rice: cultivating of the boro crop in DWR and transplanted aman fields previously infected with ufra. raising seedlings in infected fields. irrigating

seedbeds with water from infected fields, exposing fields to irrigation water from infected fields, planting infected seedlings in ufra-free areas, and selling infected seedlings.

To control this disease, farmers need to learn how to identify its symptoms early, the nature of its devastation and modes of survival and spread, and how to apply different control measures from the seedbed to the main fields. These measures will help to prevent the spread of the disease from endemic to ufra-free rainfed lowland and irrigated rice areas. ■

Effect of temperature and light on growth and sporulation of fusarium rice sheath rot

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The main causes of rice sheath rot (ShR) in Manipur, India, — *Fusarium moniliforme*, *F. graminearum*, and *F. avenaceum* (IMI 342486) — were isolated and maintained on potato

dextrose agar. We studied the effect of temperature and light on their growth and sporulation.

We aseptically cut 5-mm disks from actively growing pure cultures of ShR fungi and transferred each disk to a 100-ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 50 ml of potato dextrose broth. Sets of flasks were incubated in the dark at 5°, 10°, 15°, 20°, 25°, 30°, 35°, or 38°C for 7 d. Other flasks were kept at 26-27°C during the day and 18-19°C during the night and exposed to 24 h of light (provided by cool white fluorescent tubes [6500 °K 20

WJ]), or 24 h of darkness, or 12 h of light and 12 h of darkness for 7 d. All treatments were replicated three times for growth and three times for sporulation studies. Growth of each culture was estimated on a dry-weight basis; number of spores/ml was calculated using a hemocytometer.

F. avenaceum produced the most growth at 25°C and *F. moniliforme* and *F. graminearum* at 30 °C. None of the cultures grew at 5° or 38°C. Maximum sporulation for the fungi was at 30°C, although they did not sporulate at 5°, 10°, 15°, 35°, and 38°C (Table 1).

F. avenaceum and *F. graminearum* grew best in complete darkness but *F. moniliforme* grew best in complete light. Alternate light and darkness inhibited growth (Table 2).

F. avenaceum and *F. graminearum* produced the most spores in complete darkness. Complete light markedly inhibited their spore production. Though *F. moniliforme* produced an appreciable quantity of spores in both complete light and complete darkness, alternate light and darkness had a synergistic effect on spore production (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Effect of temperature on growth (dry weight) and sporulation of fungi associated with ShR in darkness.

Temperature (°C)	<i>F. avenaceum</i>		<i>F. moniliforme</i>		<i>F. graminearum</i>	
	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)
5	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	110	0	98	0	88	0
15	140	0	110	0	97	0
20	205	4 × 10 ²	118	4 × 10 ³	121	4 × 10 ²
25	284	4 × 10 ³	212	16 × 10 ³	183	4 × 10 ³
30	213	8 × 10 ³	317	4 × 10 ⁴	310	4 × 10 ³
35	93	0	105	0	121	0
38	0	0	0	0	0	0
CD (0.05)	4.4		4.8		4.5	

Table 2. Effect of light on growth (dry weight) and sporulation of fungi associated with ShR.

Source of light ^a	Temperature (°C)		<i>F. avenaceum</i>		<i>F. moniliforme</i>		<i>F. graminearum</i>	
	Night	Day	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)
Complete light	18-19	26-27	257	1 × 10 ²	240	4 × 10 ³	319	2 × 10 ²
Complete darkness	18-19	26-27	328	3 × 10 ³	200	4 × 10 ³	345	6 × 10 ³
Alternate light (12 h) and darkness (12 h)	18-19	26-27	190	2 × 10 ²	210	8 × 10 ³	165	4 × 10 ²

^aCrompton cool white fluorescent (2-ft) tube with electric discharge of 6500°K 20 W.